

The Possible Role of a Congolese polyherbal formula (Drepanoalpha) as source of Epigenetic Modulators in Sickle Cell Disease: A Hypothesis

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ABSTRACT

The core message of the present paper is to show how we did to transform indigenous data (Traditional Medicine) into knowledge (Science), and then translate knowledge into innovation. The anti-sickle cell anemia activity of Drepanoalpha® could be due to its epigenetic modulator effect as revealed by the testimony's of all patients received the product. Drepanoalpha® reduces the frequency of their crises and improves their general state and their hemoglobin level. All the treated patients have normal phenotype if compared them to normal individuals and have not made any more crises for more than six months last. Anthocyanins which are the biologically active secondary metabolites of this polyherbal formula are well known in the literature for their impact on epigenetic regulation.

Keyword: Sickle cell disease, Phytomedicine, Drepanoalpha®, epigenetic modulation

INTRODUCTION

Sickle cell disease (SCD) is a genetic disease in which a mutation in the gene encoding the human β -globin subunit results in replacement of β_6 glutamic acid by valine, leading to the formation of abnormal hemoglobin, Hb S. Clinical management of SCD includes medullar transplantation, repeated blood transfusion, the use of hydroxyurea (HU) and anti-malarial prophylaxis. Although, these proposed therapies are limited and even not efficient or toxic for a long time use [1-5]. Despite the fact that HU possesses epigenetic effect in SCD management, the drug is toxic [6]. Thus, there is an urgent need to find affordable and alternative drugs. Alternative strategy in the management of SCD is now focusing on the identification of epigenetic modulators agents mainly that from medicinal plants

The human β -globin gene family located on the chromosome 11 encodes five genes, ϵ , $G\gamma$, $A\gamma$, δ and β that are expressed sequentially during development. Primitive human embryonic erythropoiesis, during which ϵ -globin is expressed, first occurs in the large predominantly nucleated erythroid cells of the yolk sac blood islands. During the fetal stage of development, hematopoiesis takes place in the fetal liver and produces definitive circulating enucleated erythrocytes in which γ -globin predominates. Around the time of birth and post-natally, the bone marrow becomes the site of erythropoiesis and the β -globin gene becomes highly transcribed, along with a low level of δ -globin gene transcription. It is only at this time, after the switch from γ to β -globin synthesis, that SCD, manifest [7].

Strategies for epigenetic therapy focused on the reactivation of fetal γ -globin expression, fueled by the observation that SCD patients with more than moderate increases in Hb F levels had significantly reduced clinical symptoms [8].

EPIGENETIC TAGS AND CHROMATIN STRUCTURE IN MAMMALIAN CELLS

DNA METHYLATION

Methylation of cytosine in the CpG islands is the most common epigenetic modification affecting mammalian DNA. CpGs in the promoters of the human β -globin genes are un-methylated in erythroblasts at the developmental stages at which they are expressed and methylated in erythroblasts that do not express them or in other cell types. DNA methylation may be inhibitory for transcription, either by direct interference with transcription factor binding or, more commonly, through binding by methyl cytosine-binding proteins (MCBPs) at methylated CpG; these MCBPs can then act to recruit histone modifying enzyme-containing co-repressor complexes [7].

HISTONE MODIFICATIONS IN CHROMATIN

Recent finding indicate that the histone N-terminal tails protruding from the surface of the nucleosome are subject to a variety of covalent modifications such as acetylation and methylation. Acetylation of lysine residues in histone tails is typically associated with active genes. Such reaction has the potential to alter the chromatin fiber since it neutralizes the basic charge of lysine residues. While, methylation of lysine residues can be associated with active or repressed genes. Histone methylation provides recognition sites for the recruitment of non-histone proteins and enzymes which affect downstream gene function [7].

PLANT PHENOLICS AS MODULATORS OF EPIGENOME

DEFINITION AND ROLES

Polyphenols are naturally occurring bioactive compounds characterized by the presence of large multiples of phenol structural units. They have antioxidant actions, disease prevention properties, and therapeutic actions. Polyphenols of several sources have shown a modulator effect on epigenetic mechanisms as DNA

methylation, histone modifications and posttranscriptional regulation by microRNAs, and these mechanisms in turn, can modulate the immune system influencing both activation and differentiation of multiple cell types involved in the immune response. These phytochemical phenols as secondary metabolites in plants play key roles in plants as the ultraviolet (UV) protectants, wound-healing action, and disease and pest resistance [9].

CLASSIFICATION OF PLANT PHENOLS

Phenols of plant origin are broadly divided into three major groups such as (i) phenolic acids, (ii) flavonoids, and (iii) non flavonoid polyphenols. Flavonoids are further divided into several classes including anthocyanins, flavonols, isoflavones and flavanols [10].

PROPOSED MECHANISMS OF EPIGENETIC REGULATION BY PLANT PHENOLICS

Many mechanisms were proposed in the literature to explain the role of phenolics as epigenetic modulators. Indeed, the phenolics compounds may regulate the functions of cellular epigenome by acting as antioxidants. Phenolics also act as pro-oxidants in presence of iron (Fe^{+2}) and oxygen or in concert with oxidase enzymes and induce oxidative stress, which may cause the modulation of the cellular epigenome through oxidant and thiol-redox signaling pathway. They are also known to undergo biotransformation into metabolites that is catalyzed by the cellular phase-I and phase-II xenobiotic-metabolizing enzymes. It is possible that these metabolites regulate the cellular epigenome through signaling cascades [11].

EFFECTS OF ANTHOCYANINS ON THE NF- κ B AND OTHER SIGNAL TRANSDUCTION PATHWAYS.

Many studies indicated that the suppression of proinflammatory chemokines, growth factors, and adhesion molecules was associated with an inhibition of NF- κ B activation. NF- κ B, is an oxidative stress-sensitive transcription factor that controls expression of genes involved in the inflammatory response (inflammatory mediator). Several NF- κ B-related proinflammatory chemokines, cytokines, and mediators of inflammatory responses were shown to decrease in the plasma of humans after consumption of dietary anthocyanins suggesting the role of anthocyanins in the inhibition of NF- κ B activation. Direct inhibition of LPS-induced NF- κ B transactivation by anthocyanins was observed in human monocytes [12].

DREPANOALPHA[®]

Drepanoalpa[®] is a polyherbal medicine produced through a bio-guided based plant selection after eight years of intensive advanced laboratory research by the research team of Professor Pius T. Mpiana at the University of Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of the Congo. Drepanoalpa[®] possess a significant antisickling (normalization rate >80%) and antioxidant activities *in vitro* ($ED_{50}= 0.604 \pm 0.028\mu\text{g/mL}$) and have the medium lethal dose (LD_{50}) higher than 4000 mg/kg (in Wistar rat model). The product has non-toxic effect on immune cells and blood clotting factors. This poly-herbal formulation increases the hemoglobin rate in the rats (500-4000 mg/kg bodyweight) and preserves the histological architecture of the liver cells compared with the control. The aqueous and alcoholic extracts of Drepanoalpa[®] contain phenolic compounds especially anthocyanins as the biologically active constituents [13].

RESULT OF A PILOTE SCALE PRELIMINARY CLINICAL TRIAL

A cohort of 20 voluntary sicklers patients were treated with Drepanoalpa[®] for four week in the Democratic Republic of the

Congo especially in the Province of "Equateur": Abumombazi hospital (10 patients including one paralyzed), general hospital of Mbandaka (02 patients), general hospital of Gemena (02 patients); in Kinshasa city: Binza (02 patients), Mont Ngafula (02 patients), Mbanza lemba (01 patient), and in Bukavu city (02 patients). All these patients are well-known for their hemoglobinopathy status as revealed by electrophoresis technique. They have not gone to the school for at least a school year; the frequency of the drepanocytary crises is recurring. In human clinical use, this nutraceutical is taken three times daily for the treatment of SCD.

According to testimony's of all patients received the product, Drepanoalpa[®] reduces the frequency of their crises and improves their general state. The oral administration of Drepanoalpa[®] does not induce any signs of toxicity (no side effects). All the treated patients have normal phenotype if compared them to normal individuals and have not made any more crises for more than six months last.

CONCLUSION

The field of nutrigenomics involves the study of how genes and dietary components interact to influence human phenotype. The observation discussed in the present paper concerning the possible interaction between β^S -gene and Drepanoalpa[®] bioactive secondary metabolites revealed that further studies involving the clinical evaluation of epigenetic modification induced by such nutraceuticals in a large scale randomized trials are needed to assess the applicability of this medicinal food in endemic regions.

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